

BB 4312 ORGANIZATIONAL DEVELOPMENT AND CHANGE
INDIVIDUAL REPORT

“Multiple Case Studies”

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Abstract

This is a multiple case study report of three local cases: 1) BruTEL 's 'Going Paperless' Initiative, 2) Sumbiling Eco Village: Promoting the Ecotourism in the Temburong District, and 3) Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)'s Green Xchange Project. The objective of this report is to identify and discuss the organizational development and change strategy or strategies employed in each of the cases. The writer also discusses the key raised issues based on some scholar's planned change theories. A few recommended solutions are included in this report. It is found that communication is the most optimal strategy solution that befit into all three cases. This is because, this type of strategy is the most general and best fit to all types of interventions when planning a change within the organization.

Keywords: ODC strategies, planned change theory, Lewin's three step model, Kotter's eight step model, positive model, communication

1.0 Introduction

This multiple case study report consists of the analyses of three cases: 1) BruTEL 's 'Going Paperless' Initiative, 2) Sumbiling Eco Village: Promoting the Ecotourism in the Temburong District, and 3) Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)'s Green Xchange Project. The main objective of this multiple case study report is to identify the organizational development and change strategy or strategies employed in these three cases. The writer will first identify the key raised issues from each of these cases. These issues will later be discussed based on the organizational change theory in the Discussion section. A number of solutions will also be discussed. At the end of this report, the writer will recommend the most optimal solutions to be deployed in these cases, followed by the conclusion of this case studies.

1.1 Problem Statement

In this section, it will consists of the overview of the raised issue(s) from each of the cases (assuming the reader has read the cases mentioned).

1.1.1 BruTEL 's 'Going Paperless' Initiative

It is stated that BruTel is planning to 'go paperless' where they wished to introduce an absolute utilization of the technology in their business and omit the usage of papers. The main aim of this plan is to accomplish the third goal of BruTel i.e. to conserve the natural environment. However, some segments of its customers are giving the adverse response – especially the elder people. It is said that majority of the elderly experienced some difficulties on using the technology due to the computers incompetency which caused them to insist on the traditional system (using paper to make transactions). This therefore hinders BruTel to achieve its third goal. Hence, the main issue for BruTel is the reluctance or hesitance of these customer segments to the intended system change. It is also stated that if BruTel succeed on persuading this group of customers to switch to the new system, BruTel could smoothly develop and execute its strategies on the 'go paperless' system.

1.1.2 Sumbiling Eco Village: Promoting the Ecotourism in the Temburong District

Similar to the BruTel case, this case is also facing the challenges on implementing the green activities. It is said that Sumbiling Eco Village (SEV) is having issue in obtaining regular sources of electricity and water. This is because the location of SEV is far from the city where the flow of these sources are quite limited. Besides having a scarce source of electricity and water, SEV is also scarce in skilled workers who are well versed in the green activities. Another issue is that SEV struggles to maintain the facilities such as the benches and chairs due to the inevitable circumstances such as fluctuations in climate i.e. Brunei humid weather and the salinity of the wind (this is because SEV is located next to the salt-water river bank of Sungai Temburong). These type of nature caused the fast erosion of SEV facilities and architectures. In this regard, SEV's founder wanted help from the building schemes that utilized green practices to prolong its facilities 'endurance. Not only that, SEV also felt

threatened by the existence of other ecotourism spots in the neighbouring countries such as Sarawak and Miri; which they may have better offers in its tourism businesses. Additionally, the local communities and the indigenous cultures may also be 'polluted' by the foreign visitors and wealth. Nevertheless, SEV founder is persistent in the establishment of SEV and the founder wanted to change people's mind sets— especially the local community, about ecotourism. It is also stated that an active tourism activities in the natural areas tend to lead to environmental degradation. Therefore, it is crucial for SEV to set a thorough plans and management in order to minimize the negative impact from its activities – especially the jungle camping activities, towards the natural environment.

1.1.3 Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)'s Green Xchange Project

Last but not least, the SCOT case. It can be considered that SCOT has run its Non-Government Organization (NGO) quite well. However, there are several issues raised throughout its operation. The first issue is, SCOT is highly reliant to the donations and funding from the government and private organization. The main advantage from these donations and funding are to realize SCOT's next projects (after one project ends). This means that if there is not enough money to conduct the next project, SCOT would have difficulties in continuing the NGO to help the underprivileged people in entrepreneurship. Hence, SCOT's mission of reducing poverty could also be hindered because the underprivileged people is dependent on SCOT's project e.g. building coops for chicken rearing to earn money. In this regard, SCOT hopes that their Green Xchange project is sufficient enough to generate their own financial source. The Green Xchange project is to collect recyclable materials from the public and exchange it with basic necessities such as rice. However, through this activity, another issue arise. The price for the basic necessities are uncertain and may fluctuate as they are highly dependent to some factors such as supplier countries' climate and currency rate. This in result, will affect the price of exchange rate between recyclable materials and the basic necessities.

2.0 Discussion

This section will include the discussion of the root causes of the key raised issues. The writer will discuss these issues based on the assumed theories that is implemented in each cases based on the scholar's planned change theory. The second subsection consists of the possible solution(s) that can be employed in the respective cases.

2.1 Case Analysis

2.1.1 BruTEL's 'Going Paperless' Initiative

It is stated that BruTel is having challenges in implementing the new change initiative. It is also stated that the status quo are from some of its customer segments – particularly the elder people, where they are hesitant or resistant to the change initiative i.e. go paperless project; this project is also in line with BruTel's third goal of corporate social responsibilities (to be conservative to the natural environment). It is understood that the main cause for these resistance are because the elder people are not techno-savvy and are not familiar to the usage of technology. This indicates that BruTel's main issue is the difficulty in making the customer (elder people) to 'digest' and adapt to the new intended change (switching from traditional transaction to electronic billing). Therefore, it is assumed that BruTel is utilizing the Lewin's three step model. Lewin's three step model functions to evaluate the organizational change process; and to evaluate the challenges caused from the status quo on the implementation of the change. Beforehand, the following is the brief explanation of the three stages of Lewin's model (Cummings & Worley, 2009):

- 1) **Freezing** – at this stage, the organization prepares the initial set of activities of the intended change. This is to gently introduce the organization members or other parties on the intended change.
- 2) **Moving** – this is a process when people starts to 'digest' the new change. At this stage, status quo may still exist.
- 3) **Refreezing** – this is when people are accustomed and stabilized to the new change. And when this occur, the organization is ready to consolidate its planned change initiatives.

Referring to the above model, at the first stage, BruTel has successfully prepared the change initiative ('go paperless' initiative) as in line with its third corporate social responsibilities goal i.e. being conservative to the natural environment.

At the second stage, it is where BruTel faces the status quo of its customers (elderly), where they resist to the change of going paperless due to not being a techno-savvy and unfamiliar with the usage of technology. According to Kotter & Schlesinger (2008), these resistance to change are due to the misunderstanding and the lack of trust to the change. It is misunderstood of the boon effects of the change. These people assumes that the change would give them more bane as compared to boon. Thus, resulting in the lack of trust to the organization who implemented the change. In this case, the elder people can be considered to misunderstand of the benefit of 'go paperless' initiative.

At the final stage, as per stated in the case study, if these elder customers are successfully persuaded to switch to the new paperless system, then BruTel can proceed to develop and implement its green strategies. This indicates that BruTel's dilemma on whether to continue or stop the green initiative to accomplish its third goal. This dilemma is as a response to the non-techno-savvy customer. Hence, it is concluded that BruTel failed to proceed to the final stage of the Lewin's three step model due to the challenges of status quo caused from its elderly customers. It indicates that the main issue of BruTel is to get the change implementation to be fully digested and accepted by its elderly customers.

2.1.2 Sumbiling Eco Village: Promoting the Ecotourism in the Temburong District

It is assumed that SEV utilizes the Kotter's eight step model. Kotter's eight step model consists of the of eight stages: 1) Establishing a sense of urgency, 2) Creating the guiding coalition, 3) Developing a vision and strategy, 4) Communicating the change, 5) Empowering the broad-based action, 6) Generating short-term wins, 7) Consolidating gains and producing more change, and 8) Anchoring new approaches in the culture (Cummings & Worley, 2009). Below are the brief explanation of each stages ("The 8-Step Process", n.d.), followed by the writer's analysis based on these eight stages:

1) **Establishing a sense of urgency** – in this stage, the organization are to seek an urgent and affirmed attention from the others and telling them that change is needed within the organization. Referring this to SEV case, SEV is aware that its organization is lacking the assets such as irregular flow of electricity and water, lack of skilled employees who are well versed on the green activities, as well as lacking in maintenance capability where their architectures are easily worn out by natural processes due to its geographical factors (e.g. Brunei's humid climate and saline wind from the salt-water river beside SEV). It is also stated that SEV feels threatened by the neighbouring ecotourism businesses which may offer better services.

2) **Creating the guiding coalition** – this is a process where the organization finds the most influential person or people (within or outside the organization) to create the most effective way to telling people on the importance of the change. In this case, it is stated that SEV is trying to get connected with green building schemes to help them prolonging its architectures and facilities' endurance. It is also understood that SEV founder intends to urge the local community especially the nearby community to support SEV as it is mentioned that the nearby community are against SEV change initiative to run the ecotourism business.

3) **Developing a vision and strategy** – this phase involves the creation of the change vision in order to provide the organization members the clear idea or the rationale of the planned change. The development of strategies also takes place in this phase. Referring to the case, SEV founder explained that she intends to make its business more attractive (in architecture and services wise) in order to attract more customers, to be competitive with the other neighbouring competitors, as well as to change the community's mind sets on the ecotourism.

4) **Communicating the change** – this is where the organization members gather as many people in the organization to ensure all organization members are aware of the new change and clear of its vision. As for this stage onwards, it is not stated in the case of whether SEV has conducted the strategies based on these stages of Kotter’s eight step model. Thus, the writer assumes that SEV has not gone to this stage yet. Hence, the writer will discuss on this stages relating to SEV case study in the Alternative Solution section of this report.

5) **Empowering the broad-based action** – this phase omits as much barriers as possible e.g. hierarchical barriers, in order to promote freedom in communication and it enables the members of the organization to do their task or jobs well.

6) **Generating short-term wins** – this process involves the structuring of the short term steps towards the long term goals. It is to create the sense of winning the goals often in which this action will promote the organization members to be motivated and can perform better.

7) **Consolidating gains and producing more change** – this phase involves in the constant effort put after success in order to produce more successful changes. This process is mainly to achieve the organization’s long term vision.

8) **Anchoring new approaches in the culture** – this final stage of the planned change model consists of the conveyed connections between the new planned changes.

2.1.3 Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)’s Green Xchange Project

As for the SCOT case, it is assumed that SCOT uses the Positive model because it is stated in the case study that SCOT is focusing on its success activities to develop to a much better outcome. Positive model “*focuses on positive dynamics in organizations that give rise to extraordinary outcomes*” (Cummings & Worley, 2009). It means that the organization focuses on its good side as a driver to develop to a better outcome. Positive model has five stages: 1) Initiate the inquiry, 2) Inquire into Best Practice, 3) Discover the themes, 4) Envision a preferred future, and 5) Design and deliver ways to create the future.

1) **Initiate the Inquiry** – this is a process where the organization members identifies the main organization issue. This is when SCOT identifies that they are facing financial issue where they highly reliant to the government and private organization’s funding and donations for most of its conducted projects.

2) **Inquire into Best Practices** – in this stage, communicated information amongst the organization members are gathered; it involves the topic on what is their best attributes. It is understood that SCOT has communicated to its staffs and volunteers that their Green Xchange project is the most successful project and that has the most potential to overcome its financial issue.

3) **Discover the Themes** – this is when the organization members shares ideas or innovation of change and create the theme of change. In this phase, SCOT founder itself belief that their Green Xchange project has benefitted them

financially since it is fund-driven. This project at the same time enables them to achieve its mission on the green initiatives (raising green awareness and reducing poverty).

4) **Envision a Preferred Future** – after all information are gathered, the members identifies which theme is the most mutually agreed. The members also envision its change initiative's vision; it involves on the long term goal of the intended change. At this phase, SCOT has visualized the possible goals of its Green Xchange project where they strongly belief that this project would give them an internal financial source.

5) **Design and Deliver Ways to Create the Future** – this is the final stage of the Positive model. It involves the set of activities that are to be conducted to form and implement on the change strategies. As stated in the case study, SCOT has successfully innovate changes to achieve an even better outcome. They are also able to generate its own finance that is sufficient enough to be allocated to their next projects. Additionally, this project has also successfully promoted the public to the green awareness which is aligned with SCOT's mission. This indicates that SCOT has fully utilized this change model.

2.2 Alternative Solutions

In this section, the writer will suggest some solutions in order to overcome the issues faced in each case.

2.2.1 BruTEL's 'Going Paperless' Initiative

- It is recommended that BruTel communicate to the elderly on the actual benefit of the 'go paperless' change. This is to ensure that the elder customers are aware of the green initiative – not only to the organization itself, but to the world as a whole.
- BruTel should not completely implement the change of going paperless as according to Kotter & Schlesinger (2008), some people are limited to change that caused them to resist the change. To overcome this issue, BruTel may provide employees to guide them on how to use the technology. However, this strategy may not be as effective thus, BruTel could hire a specific employee to be assigned as the guider or helper whenever these non-techno-savvy people struggles on the new change.

2.2.2 Sumbiling Eco Village: Promoting the Ecotourism in the Temburong District

- Since it is assumed that the SEV has not fully executed its change strategies, it is recommended for the SEV to continue its strategies from developing its change vision and strategies to communicating the change. It is crucial to communicate to the whole organization of the intended change. This is to aid and guide all members of the organization to conduct and execute its respective jobs. Additionally, this step is crucial in order to avoid any

uncertainty experiences of the organization members. When they are uncertain, the change strategy would have not successfully executed.

- Next is empowering the broad-based action; this is where the organization members of SEV, especially the manager, should avoid any barriers. The barriers include, allowing rumours, strict hierarchical structures during meeting and etc. This hinders the freedom of its member to express their feedback on the intended change which may affect the effectiveness of change strategies.
- SEV also have to create appreciation more often for its employees. This is to create motivation to the employees. Thus, the employees could be motivated to exert its expertise in their jobs (e.g. survival skills for the jungle camping programme).
- As for the seventh stage of Kotter's eight step model, SEV should make continuous efforts in its strategies as SEV is an ecotourism business which most of its income are of the interaction with human. SEV should keep track of its customers' feedback on the business as a whole. SEV should also pay attention to the nearby community where one of the SEV's activity is jungle camping. This activity could or may interrupt the nearby community's routines which eventually cause them to oppose to the establishment of SEV.
- Last but not least, SEV should portray the necessity and the benefit of the implemented change. This is to help the process of adaptation and the acceptance of the new change from the respective affected parties to the SEV.

2.2.3 Society for Community Outreach and Training (SCOT)'s Green Xchange Project

- It is recommended that SCOT would have at least, another fund-generated project in order to generate its own self-financed green projects. This is to avoid limited options for its financial resources. Seeing the possibilities, if the Green Xchange project is no longer plausible to the public, then SCOT would have again dependent of other parties' funds and donations.
- SCOT should also communicate to the public in order to have an optimal effect on raising its green awareness. This action will eventually help the public to engage or participate to SCOT's green activities and thus, enabling them to accomplish their missions (i.e. raising green awareness, promoting green behaviour and reducing poverty by teaching the underprivileged people to do entrepreneurship though managing waste materials).

3.0 Recommendation

Through the analyses and the proposed solutions, it is concluded that communication is the best befitting strategy to be implemented in all three cases as this the most basic type of organizational development and change strategy. According to Kotter and Schlesinger (2008), communication is the best strategy to use when dealing with changes, especially when there is resistance to change. Communication provides people to give and take the rationale of changes. It also aids the organization member or any parties to have the clear view of what and why there is the needs to be change. Elving (2005) also mentioned in his study that communication promotes the sense of community where organization members can work in harmony. This will eventually enhances the execution of its organizational change strategies. While there may be several other solutions to overcome organizational change implementation, the writer believes that communication is the most common and the best solution to these three given cases.

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